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Spike protein related adverse effects and the need for more focused, if not individualized approach in COVID-19 vaccination programs

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ABSTRACT

Aim of this review is to discuss the need for more focused, if not individualized COVID-19 vaccination approach with a goal to prevent serious adverse effects and to establish high quality vaccination programs according to the principles of precision medicine.

KEYWORDS: covid19; vaccines; adverse effects; precision medicine

INTRODUCTION

Ten vaccines approved by World Health Organization (WHO) up-to-date are NVX-CoV2373 (Novavax, protein vaccine, Novavax), COVOVAX (Serum Institute of India, Novavax formulation), mRNA-1273 (Spikevax, mRNA vaccine, Moderna), BNT162b2 (Tozinameran, Comirnaty, mRNA vaccine, Pfizer/BioNTech), Ad26.COV2.S (Janssen, non-replicating viral vector vaccine, Johnson & Johnson), ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 (AZD1222, Vaxzevria, non-replicating viral vector vaccine, Oxford/AstraZeneca), Covishield (Serum Institute of India, Oxford/AstraZeneca formulation), BBV152 (Covaxin, inactivated virus, Bharat Biotech), BBIBP-CorV (Covilo, inactivated virus, Sinopharm, Beijing), and Sinovac (CoronaVac, inactivated virus) [1].

SPIKE PROTEIN ADVERSE EFFECTS

In a study conducted by Perry and coworkers a total number of 70 patients with VITT (vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia)-associated cerebral venous thrombosis were compared with 25 patients who developed cerebral venous thrombosis without evidence of VITT after spike protein-based vaccination, as well as with historical data from the 624 patients with cerebral venous thrombosis in the ISCVT (International Study on Cerebral Vein and Dural Sinus Thrombosis) cohort. Patients with VITT were significantly younger than patients who did not have VITT. All 70 cases of VITT-associated cerebral venous thrombosis occurred after a first dose of the ChAdOx1 (Oxford/AstraZeneca) vaccine, compared with 21 (85%) of 25 patients with non-VITT cerebral venous thrombosis, in

whom the remaining four patients had been given their first dose (three patients) or second dose (one patient) of BNT162b2 (Pfizer/BioNTech) vaccine [2].

A fatal case of VITT after receiving the first dose of the ChAdOx1 (Oxford/AstraZeneca) vaccine was reported by Aladdin and coworkers. Authors proposed that the mechanism of VITT is the production of rogue antibodies against platelet factor-4 resulting in a massive platelet aggregation, and concluded that vaccine recipients should be warned about the symptoms of VITT [3].

Another case of a previously healthy woman in her thirties with headaches that developed one week after vaccination with ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 was published. Three days later, her condition deteriorated rapidly, and she presented to the emergency department with slurred speech, uncoordinated movements and reduced consciousness. Symptoms progressed to left-sided hemiparesis and her level of consciousness deteriorated. Computed tomography (CT) of the head showed a large right-sided hemorrhage and incipient herniation. She was found to have severe thrombocytopenia $37 \times 10^9/l$, (ref 145 - $390 \times 10^9/l$). In spite of efforts to reduce intracranial pressure, the patient died the following day. *Post mortem* examination revealed antibodies to PF4, and fresh small thrombi were found in the transverse sinus, frontal lobe and pulmonary artery [4].

A case series of three women who

developed venous thromboembolism after RNA-1273 vaccination (Moderna) was published. An otherwise healthy 25-year-old woman, that had been taking oral contraceptive pills for years, presented to the emergency department 2 days after receiving the first of the mRNA-1273 vaccine series with acute-onset shortness of breath and dyspnea on exertion. Computed tomography angiography (CTA) revealed bilateral segmental pulmonary embolism (PE). Venous Doppler ultrasound scans showed no deep vein thrombosis. A 77-year-old woman with a history of gastrointestinal bleeding had presented to the emergency department with a 4-day history of shortness of breath. She had received the first of the mRNA-1273 vaccine series 3 days before symptom onset. She had a remote history of breast cancer, which had been diagnosed and treated in 2009. The CTA-PE was notable for bilateral segmental PE. Venous Doppler ultrasound scans revealed DVT of the right common femoral, femoral, and profunda veins. An 84-year-old woman had presented with an 8-day history of left leg pain and swelling. Her symptoms had started 3 days after receiving the second injection of the mRNA-1273 vaccine series. The CTA-PE showed no PE but revealed thrombus in the common femoral vein. Venous duplex ultrasound confirmed left common femoral, popliteal, and peroneal deep venous thrombosis [5].

A case of an 86-year-old man with a history of prostate cancer treated with

prostatectomy and radiotherapy, that had paroxysmal atrial fibrillation treated with apixaban, without any previous allergies to drugs or vaccines, was published. Approximately 30 minutes after the injection of the first dose of Comirnaty vaccine (Pfizer/BioNTech), the patient collapsed. An ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction of the inferior wall was diagnosed based on electrocardiogram findings, and coronary angiography revealed occlusions/distal embolization in the distal part of the left anterior descending coronary artery, in the first diagonal branch, and in the distal part of the dominant right coronary artery, with large thrombus. Despite timely treatment patient died [6].

A case report of a massive thrombosis of the entire portal venous system in a 41-year-old man with unremarkable medical history following ChAdOx1 (AstraZeneca) vaccination (first dose) was published [7].

A study describing a total of 23 male patients (22 currently serving in the military and 1 retiree; median [range] age, 25 [20-51] years), that presented with acute onset of marked chest pain within 4 days after receipt of an mRNA COVID-19 vaccine, was published. All military members were previously healthy with a high level of fitness. Seven received the BNT162b2-mRNA vaccine and 16 received the mRNA-1273 vaccine. A total of 20 patients had symptom onset following the second dose of an appropriately spaced 2-dose series. All

patients had significantly elevated cardiac troponin levels. Among 8 patients who underwent cardiac magnetic resonance imaging within the acute phase of illness, all had findings consistent with the clinical diagnosis of myocarditis. Additional testing did not identify other etiologies for myocarditis, including acute COVID-19 and other infections, ischemic injury, or underlying autoimmune conditions [8].

A study describing case series of children younger than 19 years, that were hospitalized with myocarditis within 30 days of BNT162b2 messenger RNA COVID-19 vaccine, was published. Myocarditis was diagnosed in children after COVID-19 vaccination, most commonly in boys after the second dose. In this case series, in short-term follow-up, patients were mildly affected. Authors concluded that the long-term risks associated with postvaccination myocarditis remain unknown [9].

In another study, that included the medical record from forty hospitals in Washington, Oregon, Montana and Los Angeles County, California, the number of post-vaccination myocarditis and pericarditis were analyzed. Among 2 000 287 individuals receiving at least 1 COVID-19 vaccination, 58.9% were women, the median age was 57 years, 76.5% received more than 1 dose, 52.6% received the BNT162b2 vaccine (Pfizer/BioNTech), 44.1% received the mRNA-1273 vaccine (Moderna), and 3.1% received the Ad26.COV2.S vaccine

(Janssen/Johnson & Johnson). Twenty individuals had vaccine-related myocarditis and 37 had pericarditis [10].

The *post-mortem* examination of two typical cases of the Vaxzevria vaccine-induced thrombotic thrombocytopenic syndrome (VITT) shows that the involvement of large venous vessels was much more extensive than appreciated by imaging during the brief clinical course of these fatal cases. Microscopic findings showed vascular thrombotic occlusions occurring in the microcirculation of multiple organs and increased inflammatory infiltrates. Immunohistochemical analyses highlighted the vascular and peri-vascular expression of adhesion molecules such as VICAM1, as well as the presence of CD66b+, CD163+ and CD61+ activated inflammatory cells, also expressing C1r. Authors concluded that these findings indicate that the activation of the innate immune system and complement pathway promote the inflammatory process leading to the microvascular damage of multiple organs [11].

A case report of a 52-years old male, that developed sudden-onset reading difficulty and aphasia seven days after the second dose of an mRNA-based SARS-CoV-2 vaccine, was published. He had a previous history of myocardial infarction, arterial hypertension, hyperlipidemia, and nephrolithiasis. Blood pressure was slightly elevated on admission. Blood tests revealed mildly elevated D-dimer, pre-diabetes and

hyperuricemia. Cerebral magnetic resonance imaging revealed an intracerebral bleeding (ICB) in the left temporal lobe. Aphasia resolved almost completely within a few days [12].

A study aimed to compare the clinical presentations and courses of VITT between the two adenoviral vector vaccines, Ad26.COV.2.S (Janssen/Johnson & Johnson) and ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 (Astra-Zeneca), was published. Authors found that cerebral venous thrombosis (CVT) after Ad26.COV.2.S vaccination presents later with similar symptoms compared to CVT after administration of ChAdOx1 nCoV-19, albeit with more thrombosis and intracerebral hemorrhage, lower D-dimer and aPTT levels, but similar mortality [13].

A case of a healthy 63-year-old woman with no cardiovascular risk factors, that was admitted to the emergency room with new-onset dyspnea and fever, was published. The symptoms started 1 day after receiving the first of two mRNA-1273 (Moderna, Cambridge, MA, USA) COVID-19 vaccinations. Cardiac magnetic resonance imaging (CMR) showed extensive oedema in the mid-ventricular/apical segments. Authors concluded that the most probable diagnosis is COVID-19 vaccine-induced Takotsubo cardiomyopathy [14].

A case of 28-year-old healthy female, that developed muscle pain of her thigh muscles, radiating to the lower legs, accompanied by an asymmetrical weakness of

the lower limbs, five days after her first dose of Moderna mRNA vaccine, was published. Seven days following vaccination, a blood test revealed marked elevation of creatine kinase and transaminases. An MRI of the thigh muscles showed left-dominant edematous signal alterations with contrast enhancement of the quadriceps muscles sparing the *M. rectus femoris*, and diffuse subcutaneous fluid retention with contrast enhancement, suggestive of fasciitis. Electromyography of the left rectus muscle showed positive sharp waves and fibrillations with small and partly polyphasic motor unit potentials, compatible with an acute myopathy or myositis. The patient was treated with an intravenous cycle of 250 mg methylprednisolone over 2 days, leading to complete remission of paresis, leg pain and remission of leg edema within days, followed by oral tapering (60 mg methylprednisolone orally, tapered over 6 days), with complete recovery [15].

SARS-CoV-2 vaccination associated Guillain-Barré syndrome (GBS) is increasingly recognized as a complication of SARS-CoV-2 vaccinations, why neurologists should stay alert not to miss the causal relation [16].

In a case report, authors described a 32-year-old previously healthy man who developed acute confusion, memory disturbances, and auditory hallucination within 24 hours from getting his first dose of the COVID-19 Moderna vaccine. EEG

showed features of encephalopathy. Patient improved dramatically after receiving methylprednisolone. Authors concluded that COVID-19 vaccine was the only possible cause of encephalopathy in this patient [17].

As of March 21, the Yellow Card-reported frequency of facial paralysis or paresis and facial nerve disorder after any dose was close to 23 per million with the Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine and 13 per million with the Oxford-AstraZeneca vaccine. Excluding reports of facial paralysis cross-listed with cerebrovascular accident, EudraVigilance data indicate a much higher frequency of facial paralysis after the Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine than after the Oxford-AstraZeneca vaccine (497 vs 56 cases or 13.6 vs 4.1 per million doses as of April 3). The risk of developing facial paralysis could be two to three times higher in individuals receiving mRNA vaccines than in those receiving traditional vaccines [18].

A case of new-onset refractory status epilepticus (NORSE) after receiving the first dose of the ChAdOx1 (AstraZeneca) vaccine was published. The patient had recurrent seizures that were refractory to conventional antiepileptic drug therapy with a dramatic response to immunotherapy with pulse steroids and plasmapheresis. Authors concluded that this likely reflects an underlying autoimmune mechanism in the genesis of post-vaccination generalized seizures without fever [19].

A case report of a 33-year-old healthy

Hispanic male, that referred to the ophthalmology service due to blurry vision and metamorphopsia in the right eye without any flashes, floaters, eye redness or pain, was published. The patient reported that 69 hours prior to presentation he received the first dose of the Pfizer-BioNTech BNT162b2 mRNA COVID-19 vaccine. He denied any past ocular history or pertinent medical history. He did not take any medicines and denied any stressful factors in his life. The clinical examination and imaging tests were consistent with central serous retinopathy that resolved in three months [20].

A case report of a new-onset renal-limited ANCA-associated vasculitis (AAV) in a 78-year-old woman with previously normal kidney function after receiving the Pfizer/BioNTech COVID-19 vaccine, was published. The patient developed acute kidney injury with proteinuria and microscopic hematuria with many dysmorphic red blood cells in the urine. Anti-myeloperoxidase antibody titer was elevated. Kidney biopsy showed pauci-immune crescentic necrotizing glomerulonephritis. Kidney function improved after treatment with steroids and rituximab [21].

A case of a 63-year-old man without a history of autoimmunity or SARS-CoV-2 natural infection who experienced acute severe autoimmune-like hepatitis seven days after the first dose of the mRNA-1273 SARS-CoV-2 vaccine, was published. Liver histology showed inflammatory portal

infiltrate with interface hepatitis, lobular and centrilobular inflammation with centrilobular necrosis, in absence of fibrosis and steatosis. Serum immunoglobulin G was slightly elevated. Autoimmune liver serology showed an indirect immunofluorescence pattern on triple rodent tissue compatible with anti-mitochondrial antibody (AMA), but, unexpectedly, this pattern was not mirrored by positivity for primary biliary cholangitis (PBC)-specific molecular tests, indicating that this antibody is different from classical AMA. Anti-nuclear antibody (ANA) was also positive with a rim-like indirect immunofluorescence pattern on liver and HEp2 cell substrates, similar to PBC-specific ANA; however, anti-gp210 and a large panel of molecular-based assays for nuclear antigens were negative, suggesting a unique ANA in this patient, who also carries the HLA DRB1*11:01 allele, which is protective against PBC. Response to prednisone treatment was satisfactory [22].

A rare case of a bi-facial diplegia variant of Guillain-Barré syndrome (GBS), within four weeks of the Janssen COVID-19 vaccination, was published. Due to its chronology, clinical manifestations, and cerebrospinal fluid findings, authors proposed this case to be a rare complication of the COVID-19 vaccination [23].

Two cases of malignant middle cerebral artery (MCA) infarct and thrombocytopenia 9-10 days following ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccination were

published. Patient 1 was a 57-year-old woman who underwent decompressive craniectomy despite two prior, successful mechanical thrombectomies. Patient 2 was a 55-year-old woman who developed a fatal bilateral malignant MCA infarct. Both patients manifested pulmonary and portal vein thrombosis and high level of antibodies to platelet factor 4-polyanion complexes. None of the patients had ever received heparin in the past before stroke onset [24].

Two cases of an acute myocardial infarction with onset less than 24 hours after the first dose of mRNA-1273 (Moderna) COVID-19 vaccine in patients presenting with shoulder pain, were published [25].

A case of a 57-year-old female, who presented 1 week after receiving the second dose of the Pfizer vaccine with subacute onset of intense burning dysesthesias in the feet, gradually spreading to the calves and minimally into the hands, unaccompanied by other neurological or constitutional symptoms, was published. A diagnosis of biopsy-proven small fiber neuropathy as a post-vaccination complication was established [26].

IMPORTANT *IN VITRO* STUDIES

In a study, by using an *in vitro* cell line, researchers reported that the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein significantly inhibits DNA damage repair, which is required for effective V(D)J recombination in adaptive immunity. Mechanistically, researchers found that the

spike protein localizes in the nucleus and inhibits DNA damage repair by impeding key DNA repair protein BRCA1 and 53BP1 recruitment to the damage site [27].

In another study researchers investigated the interaction of S2 subunit to tumor suppressor and cell cycle-related proteins. HADDOCK 2.2 software was used to analyze the interaction and found that S2 subunit of SARS-nCoV-2 strongly interacts with p53 and BRCA-1/2 proteins, which are tumor suppressor proteins, that regulate downstream genes in response to numerous cellular stresses and are frequently mutated in human cancer [28].

In a study, researchers investigated the effect of BNT162b2 on the human liver cell line Huh7 *in vitro*. Huh7 cells were exposed to BNT162b2, and quantitative PCR was performed on RNA extracted from the cells. High levels of BNT162b2 were detected in Huh7 cells and changes in gene expression of long interspersed nuclear element-1 (LINE-1), which is an endogenous reverse transcriptase. Immunohistochemistry using antibody binding to LINE-1 open reading frame-1 RNA-binding protein (ORFp1) on Huh7 cells treated with BNT162b2 indicated increased nucleus distribution of LINE-1. PCR on genomic DNA of Huh7 cells exposed to BNT162b2 amplified the DNA sequence unique to BNT162b2. Authors concluded that these results indicate a fast uptake of BNT162b2 into human liver cell line Huh7, leading to changes in LINE-1 expression and

distribution. Authors also showed that BNT162b2 mRNA is reversely transcribed intracellularly into DNA in as fast as 6 hours upon BNT162b2 exposure [29].

INCREASING EPIDEMIOLOGICAL RELEVANCE OF COVID-19-VACCINATED POPULATION

Although high COVID-19 vaccination rates were expected to reduce transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in populations by reducing the number of possible sources for transmission, recent data indicate that the epidemiological relevance of COVID-19 vaccinated individuals is increasing. In the UK it was described that secondary attack rates among household contacts exposed to fully vaccinated index cases was similar to household contacts exposed to unvaccinated index cases (25% versus 23%). Peak viral load does not differ by vaccination status or variant type. In Germany, the rate of symptomatic COVID-19 cases among the fully vaccinated is increasing week by week providing clear evidence of the increasing relevance of the fully vaccinated as a possible source of transmission. A similar situation was described for the UK. In Israel a nosocomial outbreak was reported involving 16 healthcare workers, 23 exposed patients and two family members. The vaccination rate was 96.2% among all exposed individuals. Fourteen fully vaccinated patients became severely ill or died, the two unvaccinated patients developed mild disease.

CDC identifies four of the top five counties with the highest percentage of fully vaccinated population as high transmission counties [30].

CROSS-REACTIVE MEMORY T-CELLS

Kundu and coworkers published a study in which they assessed 52 COVID-19 household contacts to capture immune responses at the earliest timepoints after SARS-CoV-2 exposure. Using a dual cytokine FLISpot assay on peripheral blood mononuclear cells, researchers enumerated the frequency of T cells specific for spike, nucleocapsid, membrane, envelope and ORF1 SARS-CoV-2 epitopes that cross-react with human endemic coronaviruses. Researchers observed higher frequencies of cross-reactive ($p=0.0139$), and nucleocapsid-specific ($p=0.0355$) IL-2 secreting memory T cells in contacts who remained PCR-negative despite exposure ($n=26$), when compared with those who convert to PCR-positive ($n=26$), whilst no significant difference in the frequency of responses to spike is observed, hinting at a limited protective function of spike-cross-reactive T cells. Authors concluded that these results are consistent with pre-existing non-spike cross-reactive memory T cells protecting SARS-CoV-2 naive contacts from infection, thereby supporting the inclusion of non-spike antigens, especially ORF1 and N (nucleocapsid) antigens, in second-generation vaccines against COVID-19 [31].

DISCUSSION

Case reports of serious adverse effects of COVID-19 vaccines presented in this article are just examples of up-to-date available published scientific literature on this subject, number of which now exceeds thousand. It is plausible to presume that the number of unpublished and unreported adverse effects are much higher. In the context of the emergence of new strains, such as Omicron (32 mutations in the spike protein) and IHU (46 mutations in the spike protein), and waning efficacy of the up-to-date available vaccines, all of which are based on the Wuhan strain (Wuhan spike protein, inactivated Wuhan virus), there is a need for more focused approach in COVID-19 vaccination programs. Individuals without risk factors for the development of severe COVID-19 and with robust natural immunity against SARS-CoV-2 (proven with T-cell test and/or serology), might not have obvious clinical benefit from the Wuhan spike protein based COVID-19 vaccination, especially when taking into account that COVID-19 vaccination does not prevent the transmission of the virus. On the other hand, high-risk individuals without natural immunity against SARS-CoV-2 have more obvious clinical benefit from the COVID-19 vaccination, although a new generation of vaccines might be necessary because of the emergence of vaccine-resistant strains. Therefore, compulsory COVID-19 vaccination might not be an appropriate approach. In addition to

that, taking into account above mentioned *in vitro* studies that show how spike protein can inhibit DNA damage repair by impeding key DNA repair protein BRCA1 and 53BP1 recruitment to the damage site, and that S2 subunit of SARS-CoV-2 strongly interacts with p53 and BRCA-1/2 proteins, which are tumor suppressor proteins, that regulate downstream genes in response to numerous cellular stresses and are frequently mutated in human cancer, there is a need for additional animal toxicological studies, in order to exclude or confirm cancerogenic and/or genotoxic potential of the spike protein, and its cumulative toxicity, before proceeding with endless booster shots of the spike protein. Finally, when taking into account the rising epidemiological relevance of COVID-19-vaccinated individuals, the strategy of compulsory COVID-19 vaccination and obligatory COVID-19 passports should be critically and openly discussed.

CONCLUSION

Taking into account the limited protective function of spike-cross-reactive T cells and more effective protective function of N- and ORF-1-cross-reactive T cells as demonstrated in the above mentioned study (Kundu et al), the toxicity of the spike (S) protein, serious adverse effects reported for Wuhan spike protein-based up-to-date available vaccines, the increasing epidemiological relevance of the COVID-19 vaccinated population, and the emergence of

new, increasingly vaccine-resistant strains with significant number of mutations in the S protein, such as Omicron with 32 mutations in S protein and IHU with 46 mutations in S protein, there is a need for the development of a new generation of COVID-19 vaccines, based on non-spike antigens, preferably ORF1 and N antigens, that would be theoretically less toxic, associated with less serious adverse effects, and more effective against emerging new strains, attributable to the cross reactive ORF-1 and N specific T-cells, but more research is mandatory.

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